

Interview Patrick Dabas – Ailes Anciennes Toulouse
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

- Presentation of the institution

Ailes Anciennes Toulouse (AA-T) is an association founded in 1980, inspired by the Ailes Anciennes at Le Bourget (AA-LB). AA-T was inspired by the collaboration, still ongoing, between AA-LB and le Musée de l'Air et de l'Espace for the restoration of exposed aircrafts.

The association counts 300 members, among which 100 are active members. Members are former aeronautical mechanics, pilots, general aviation enthusiasts.

Hourglass-shaped age pyramid. Association counts many quite young or quite old members, many of whom work or used to work as subcontractors for Airbus.

Patrick Dabas is the current President of AA-T.

The collection includes approximately 110 aircrafts, as well as numerous parts like engines and accessories. The collection includes 2 pieces related to the Procraft theme : a Morane-Saulnier aircraft (1951) and an Espadon prototype (1949).

Morane-Saulnier 733: it is not entirely clear how the aircraft integrated AA-T's collection. Probably a donation 20 years ago, from a person who had bought a group of these planes from a flight school. The association wished to have an aircraft of this type.

Espado aircraft: has been recovered on a shooting range in Champagne, by the sister association Ailes Anciennes Alsace and donated to AA-T. It's a historical aircraft. AA-T accepted it but without really wanting it. The aircraft has been stored in an unknown place for many years until it was moved to the current premises. It has been kept outdoors for the last 6 years.

These collections come mainly from donations or exchanges with other associations or museums. AA-T is not much involved with wrecks coming from underwater or land recoveries.

The association chooses to present static collections, does not wish to bring the aircrafts back to flying condition. The main reasons for this choice is the lack of financial means and the lack of skills among the members to reach flying conditions.

They will maybe create a tandem with another association who flies planes from the 1950's and 1960's.

In 2015, the association has moved on its current premises, near the Blagnac airport. They have room for workshops and offices, and share the space with 2 other associations (Cap Avenir Concorde et Aérothèque).

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects?

PD considers a wreck is an aircraft that can no longer fly. The association can also be faced with « composite planes »: this definition applies to planes of certain type carrying the manufacturer's plate of another type/number.

AA-T are completely in control of their projects, and decide on the general orientations, such as the needs and amount of replacement or repair for the various parts.

AA-T has an agreement with Aeroscopia, to which they provide a certain number of planes for display. Currently AA-T has 25 planes there.

At the same time, AA-T also have their own exhibition on their premises and they organise on site-visits directly.

Both exhibition spaces have their own identity, where collections are presented in a different perspective. Aeroscopia has more of a « museum » feeling, whereas the presentations on site have more of an « workshop » spirit.

- Concept of “conservation” : Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of “conservation” mean to you for this kind of heritage? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution?

For PD and the association, wrecks are to be kept in condition, to look at them. There is no intention to bring them back to their initial condition. PD believes it is possible to value wrecks without trying to remake them.

Morane Saulnier aircraft (Procraft number MS733-TOU) : the original central section will not be reassembled on the aircraft, it has been replaced.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly? (addition to Form A)

Interventions are carried out by a team of technicians, aged 30-40 years old, who work in the aircraft industry . They recommend what needs to be done and they can also supply or manufacture parts (directly or in collaboration with technical high-schools).

There is no contact with conservators.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A)?

None of the aircrafts are intended for flying.

No preventive conservation for the 2 aircrafts included in the Procraft project. They are kept outdoors.

The objectives for preservations can be very different from one aircraft to another. For the Morane-Saulnier the goal is renovation, for historical representation. For the Espadon, the goal is to keep it as it is.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation ? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

The 2 aircrafts included in Procraft are kept outdoors.

The association has a shed on their new premises, but that is not a space for storage or presentation. (Other aircrafts are presented indoors at Aeroscopia.)

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections ?

Exchanges and collaboration with other associations have been limited in the past years, as one can find some competitive spirit in some relationships. Associations how choose to fly their aircrafts can consider themselves superior to the associations who choose not to.

Since he became president, PD has started a Tour de France of associations, to learn to know each other and create again the conditions for initiating aircraft swaps.

AA-T is also in relation to the public authorities, who can help them, and gets involved in local politics. PD has had a meeting with General Satenay, from the Army's Heritage Departement.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant) ? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A) ?

The Morane-Saunier was considered in good condition when it arrived, in any case Al corrosion was not visible yet.

No particular focus on Al alloys.

PD is aware some aircrafts, like the Espadon, degrade being kept outdoors.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

AA-T has a rather heterogeneous collection. They try to have consistent ranges of aircrafts, but there is no real consistency. They are not trying to bring out specific themes. AA-T is interested in all artefacts with either iconic, exceptional or historical value to aeronautical heritage in general. They also have a focus on local history.